

Design of a Lift-up AGV

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Abstract: Lift-up AGV is a one kind of AGV which can use lifting mechanism to pull up the heavy instruments. So, this research focuses on the details of the lift-up AGV. To maximize load handling, navigation, and operating efficiency, this research focuses on the design and execution of an AGV with certain technological specifications. Using differential drive for improved mobility and magnetic navigation for accurate movement, the AGV is built with a 400 kg load capacity. A minimal turning radius of 650mm and a positioning and navigation precision of ± 10 mm are important technological features that provide accurate control in small areas. A strong jacking structure that can elevate weights to a height with a placement precision of ± 10 mm is integrated into the AGV, and this structure is essential to its operation. A Limetech push rod motor, model LAP25, powers the jacking mechanism. It was chosen for its small size, high torque output, and dependability. The lifting mechanism uses four linear bearing bases. This arrangement ensures stability and smooth operation. To endure operational loads and offer a sturdy basis for its subsystems, the AGV's chassis is built from high-strength steel (Q345). With its overall measurements' of 1500 mm in length, the AGV offers a small footprint with ample room for the load and internal components. With two big wheels and four tiny caster wheels, the driving system provides a balance of mobility and stability. Reduction motors power the big wheels, while caster wheels provide seamless direction changes. In terms of control and safety, the AGV is equipped with a crystal oscillator circuit for precise timing and synchronization of the onboard systems. The navigation system is supported by a suite of sensors, including obstacle detection and position tracking, ensuring reliable and accurate guidance. An emergency stop switch is incorporated to immediately halt the AGV in case of emergencies, enhancing operational safety. Two batteries are part of the electrical system of the AGV, which allows for longer operation times. To maximize energy efficiency and minimize space utilization, each battery is small and made to fit inside the AGV's chassis. Additionally, the design has features that make maintenance and battery replacement simple. Several technical requirements are outlined to guarantee that the AGV satisfies operational demands. These include of a large load capacity, accurate positioning and navigation, sturdy lifting and jacking mechanisms, dependable driving and control systems, and an abundance of safety measures. The materials chosen, which include corrosion-resistant coatings and high-strength steel, provide life and durability in a range of working conditions.

Key words: lifting AGV; Differential drive; Magnetic navigation.

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Accepted: 22 November, 2024; **Published:** 23 November, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Alauddin Himel, Md Rakibul Islam, Mubin Musavvir Sun (2024). Design of a lift-up AGV. *North American Academic Research*, 7(11), 101-142. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14553670>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Research Background: The AGV is a self-guided vehicle with automatic guidance function, which can run along a pre-laid path, security capability and transplanting function. Its advantage lies in that it can improve the intelligent degree of the factory, and the path planning can be completed by computer or embedded controller, and the occupation of human resources can be reduced. At the same time, because it can work continuously, and the error rate is low, but also can greatly improve the efficiency of production. These autonomous vehicles go along pre-planned routes while carrying out various jobs including moving raw materials, finished goods, and objects that are still being worked on. More complex and customized AGV systems are being researched because of the growing need for automation and the requirement for accuracy in material handling. AGVs were originally used as towing vehicles in production settings in the 1950s, marking the beginning of their history. With the development of sophisticated navigation systems, better weight carrying capacities, and improved control mechanisms, technology has advanced significantly over the years. The versatility and adaptability of early AGVs were restricted by their reliance on fixed-path navigation techniques like magnetic tapes or hidden cables. But AGVs have grown more effective and adaptable since the introduction of contemporary navigation technologies including magnetic, vision-based, and laser navigation [1]. In industries where big and bulky products need to be moved, load management is very important when designing AGVs. With its capacity to manage weights up to 400 kg, the AGV under development finds usage in a variety of industries, including warehouse logistics and the automobile industry. With its weight capacity, the jacking structure needs to be strong and long-lasting, able to precisely raise and place loads. For the jacking mechanism to function effectively and dependably, a Limetech push rod motor—which is renowned for its small size and strong torque output—is included. The AGV's control and safety systems are also crucial. Accurate timing and synchronization of the several subsystems depend on the exact clock signals provided by an integrated crystal oscillator circuit. Safety elements like an emergency stop button are essential because they provide the AGV the ability to stop quickly in an emergency, preventing accidents and guaranteeing the security of people and property [2]. Two batteries are incorporated into the electrical system design, which offers enough power for prolonged operating times. Energy density, weight, and maintenance simplicity are all considered while selecting batteries. Maintaining the AGV's productivity and reducing downtime require a steady power supply. By concentrating on certain technological improvements and the integration of cutting-edge components, the present gaps in AGV technology. Enhancing operational efficiency, accuracy, and safety in industrial settings is the goal of developing an AGV with these specifications. The focus on strong design, dependable navigation, and extensive safety measures is in line with the growing need for automated systems that can function in a variety of demanding environments.

Significance of research: The need of creating a highly customized Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) with exact technical specifications in the quickly changing industrial environment of today cannot be emphasized. The use of sophisticated AGV systems has become essential as enterprises aim for higher levels of production, efficiency, and safety. Several essential demands in contemporary manufacturing and logistics are addressed by this research, which focuses on the design and implementation of an AGV with magnetic navigation, differential drive, and strong load-handling capabilities. This research is important because it has the potential to improve operational efficiency. The high demands of modern industrial environments may be beyond the capabilities of traditional material handling systems, which frequently rely on manual labor or less advanced automated alternatives. The AGV can handle complicated settings with great accuracy and flexibility because to the integration of differential drive and magnetic navigation. Throughput is increased and mistake risk is decreased thanks to the magnetic navigation system's dependable path following, which

is guaranteed even in busy and dynamic surroundings [3]. In industries where accuracy and dependability are critical, such as automobile production, electronics assembly, and warehouse logistics, this improvement is especially important. The emphasis on load handling is another important component of this study. An essential need in many industrial applications is met by the AGV's capacity to carry weights up to 400 kg with a high degree of precision ($\pm 10\text{mm}$). This feature is especially important for businesses that deal with huge, heavy products, such as equipment parts, automobile parts, and large-scale packing. Through accurate load management, the AGV lowers the possibility of product damage, which lowers operating expenses and boosts total output. To further improve operational efficacy, the jacking mechanism's incorporation of a Limetech push rod motor boosts the lifting process's dependability and efficiency. This research expands the capabilities of AGVs from a technical standpoint. A major improvement over conventional AGV systems is provided by the combination of magnetic navigation, differential drive, and accurate load management. In addition to improving AGV capabilities, this research establishes a new benchmark for future advancements in the industry. The knowledge gathered from this study will help shape the conception and use of AGVs of the future, spurring more advancements in automation technology [4]. The research also has wider ramifications for the incorporation of AGVs in Industry 4.0 and smart factory settings. The importance of AGVs in enabling smooth material movement and real-time data sharing increases as workplaces become more automated and networked. The platform for incorporating sophisticated AGVs into various settings is provided by this study, enabling more responsive and effective production procedures.

Status of technology at home and abroad: In the 1950s, the British business was the first to construct an AGV system. This technology replaced the ground guide rail by laying electromagnetic lines underground, resulting in an electromagnetic-based AGV. Promoted the use of AGVs in industrial operations and storage. In the 1960s, the computer field witnessed quick and massive development and began to be utilized frequently in the AGV sector, resulting in a jump in AGV system technology, allowing it to be incorporated into several flexible industrial manufacturing processes. In the country, automated warehouses and smart factories are starting to view AGVs as essential elements [6]. Integrating cutting-edge navigation technology is one of the main themes in the domestic AGV industry. AGVs can now operate with extreme accuracy and flexibility thanks to the widespread use of magnetic navigation, laser-guided systems, and vision-based navigation. Especially in regulated conditions, magnetic navigation has become more and more common due to its dependability and simplicity of use. This technique is preferred in sectors where accuracy and consistency are essential, such as electronics and the automobile industry.

The enhancement of load management mechanisms and increased load capabilities are now commonplace in AGVs. These automated guided vehicles (AGVs) are engineered to precisely and effectively handle an array of materials, ranging from lightweight components to massive equipment parts. These AGVs can function under harsh industrial conditions since they are equipped with sturdy lifting frames and high-torque motors. While AGV technology development has similarities throughout

locations, there are also clear variances that are influenced by regional technological capabilities and industry demands. In order to satisfy the unique requirements of industrial and logistical operations, improvements in navigation accuracy, load handling, and energy efficiency have been prioritized domestically. On the other hand, increased autonomy, AI integration, and smooth system interoperability are frequently highlighted in global advances. An important area of convergence is the focus on dependability and safety. Advanced safety elements are fitted into both local and foreign AGVs to guarantee safe operation in dynamic and unexpected conditions [7]. The application of precision control systems, emergency stop mechanisms, and collision avoidance systems highlights the global dedication to developing AGV solutions that are both safe and effective. Future developments in artificial intelligence are anticipated to drive the global AGV market toward the development of more autonomous and intelligent AGVs. It is also projected that 5G integration would transform AGV communication by enabling quicker and more dependable data sharing. The creation of sustainable AGV solutions, such as those that make use of eco-friendly materials and renewable energy sources, is also anticipated to gain popularity as businesses work to lessen their environmental effect.

Fig. 2: AGV navigational order

Main Research Content: This study's primary research goal is to create, deploy, and optimize an automated guided vehicle (AGV) with precise technical specifications that will improve productivity, accuracy, and safety in industrial settings. The study is divided into many major domains, all of which focus on important facets of AGV functioning and design. The transmission mechanism's design and drawing must be finished for mechanical design to proceed. The primary program design, electrical component selection design, electrical wire diagram design, and hardware design are all completed by hardware design. As a result, the study may be categorized into three areas: software design, hardware design, and structural design. The driving wheels, reduction motors, and lifting devices will be chosen in this article depending on the AGV's load, and their installation structures will be designed and calculated to determine the AGV chassis' dimensions. The electrical appliances will be finished in accordance with their functions after the mechanical construction design is finished. To improve operating efficiency, accuracy, and safety in industrial settings, this research attempts to create an advanced AGV that satisfies strict technological standards. This study adds to the development of AGV technology and its uses in contemporary manufacturing and logistics by covering important issues including navigation, load handling, drive systems, safety, power management, and system integration. The study's

discoveries and insights might lead to major advancements in AGV deployment and design, advancing the overarching objectives of automation and efficiency in industrial processes [8].

Mechanical Part Designing

Design Structure/ overall size planning: The overall size planning of the AGV involves determining optimal dimensions to ensure stability, maneuverability, and efficient space utilization. The AGV's base chassis, which is rectangular in shape, is intended to offer stability. This project designs an AGV logistics car based on magnetic navigation, which is suitable for workshops with relatively fixed production processes. The car body is required to be compact and suitable for occasions with small logistics channels. The use of mature rail navigation technology makes AGV travel and positioning more stable and reliable. When the battery is low, it will go to the charging station for automatic charging. Mechanical design requires the completion of the design and drawing of the transmission mechanism. Hardware design completes the main electrical component selection design and electrical wiring diagram design and completes the main program design. As a result, the study topics may be classified into three categories: structural design, hardware design, and software design. This article will pick the driving wheels, reduction motors, and lifting devices based on the AGV's load, and then design and calculate their installation structures to determine the size of the AGV chassis. After the mechanical structural design is accomplished, the electrical appliances will be built according to their purposes. Select components, place them on the mechanical framework, and lastly finish designing the software component.

Design of Transmission: For the AGV to effectively transfer the motor's power into movement, the transmission design is essential. With its differential drive system—two wheels on either side of the vehicle that are separately driven—the AGV can precisely manage its speed and direction by adjusting the speed of each wheel. Big wheels with the right tread and diameter are chosen to provide the best possible traction and stability. These wheels are positioned to provide a 650mm minimum turning radius, which makes it easier to drive in confined areas. High-torque DC motors—are chosen for the AGV because of their dependability and efficiency in handling loads and operating demands. In order to improve torque and regulate wheel speed, a reduction equipment is integrated with the motors. This lowers the high-speed rotation of the motor and increases torque for more smoothly executed acceleration and deceleration. Securing traction and stability requires the use of large drive wheels with suitable tread patterns that are fixed on sturdy axles that can bear the weight and manage the torque produced by the motors. Because the transmission system and the AGV control system are linked, precise wheel speed and direction control is possible, guaranteeing smooth, well-coordinated motions that are necessary for precision navigation and load management.

Transplanting Mechanism: In order to provide effective and reliable load transfer, the transplanting design places a strong emphasis on the AGV's lifting and load handling capabilities. A Limetech push rod motor LAP25 powers the AGV's lifting mechanism, which can raise up to 400 kg of weight to a predetermined height. Four linear bearings hold the circular base plate in place, ensuring steady and seamless lifting operations. In order to give the circular lifting plate a firm platform, distribute the load equally, and avoid instability or tipping during raising, a rectangular support plate is used. The lifting plate is guided in its vertical movement by four linear bearing bases, which eliminate wear and friction and guarantee accurate and seamless operations. The push rod motor is chosen for dependable and effective operations because of its capacity to deliver a constant lifting force and because its specifications fit the demands of the load. The lifting design has safety features including overload prevention and emergency stops to prevent mishaps and guarantee safe operation, which is essential for avoiding equipment damage and guaranteeing operator safety.

Hardware Part Designing

Motor Selection: A crucial component of the AGV's hardware design is the motor selection. When selecting motors, consideration must be given to how well they can deliver the torque and speed required to drive the AGV under a variety of load scenarios. Because of their efficiency, dependability, and controllability, high-torque DC motors are used in this design. Even with the AGV fully loaded, smooth and stable movement is guaranteed by these motors, which have a 400 kg load capability. Precision motions are made possible by the reduction gearbox built into the motors, which improves torque and offers improved speed control. Due to the independent management of each motor, the differential drive system guarantees that the AGV can easily maneuver through narrow places and turn sharply [9]. The AGV operates with maximum performance, stability, and maneuverability thanks to the combination of high-torque motors and a differential drive system.

Processor Selection: The AGV's overall performance and dependability are greatly impacted by the processor choice, which is a crucial component. The compact size, high processing power, and adaptability of a single-chip microcomputer controller make it the preferred choice for this design. The microcontroller in question is a perfect fit for overseeing the AGV's many operations due to its ability to manage intricate control algorithms and real-time processing needs. To ensure that the AGV maintains precise location within a tolerance of ± 10 mm, the controller is in charge of processing inputs from a variety of sensors, including those for magnetic navigation. For the AGV to travel through narrow places and carry out intricate tasks needed in industrial settings, precision control is crucial. The microprocessor controls motor control, lifting mechanisms, and safety systems in addition to navigation. Because of its strong computing power, sophisticated functions including collision avoidance, obstacle recognition, and effective path planning may be implemented. The efficiency and dependability of the AGV are increased by the microcontroller's smooth integration with other hardware elements, which guarantees coordinated functioning. Even when the AGV is completely loaded, smooth and reliable movements are dependent on its real-time processing capacity. This microcontroller's selection also facilitates the inclusion of upcoming updates and new features, making the AGV a scalable and future-proof solution. All things considered, using a high-performance single-chip microcomputer controller guarantees that the AGV can satisfy the rigorous specifications of many industrial applications, offering a dependable and effective automated transport solution.

Overall Design

The characteristics of the workplace: AGV is usually used in digital production workshops or warehousing logistics. The working environment of the two and the requirements for AGV are relatively similar. Let's introduce their working environments. From the ground environment point of view, both are required to be smooth and crack-free, but not too smooth, impact-resistant, water-resistant, heat-resistant, acid and alkali resistant. Relatively speaking, in the warehousing environment, there are clearer requirements for the load-bearing capacity of the ground and lower requirements for chemical properties. These settings have a number of obstacles and dynamic aspects, which is one of their main features. In terms of logistics, the necessary functions of both include precise control of all links and elements of the planning and scheduling process, logistics in production, and equipment management. Usually through the deployment of wireless networks, it is easy to display the relationship between people and things, and between things in real time, to build a visual logistics system. The arrangement and surface of the floor are important components of the work environment. Different flooring kinds, such as tile, concrete, and epoxy-coated surfaces, may have varied friction and cleanliness levels, and these surfaces must be traversed by AGVs. AGVs also need to maneuver through tight spaces, tight curves, and inclination, all of which might be present in the environment's layout. The AGV's suspension, drive system, and wheel type must all be adjusted for handling these circumstances without sacrificing stability or load balancing.

AGVs are frequently used in a variety of lighting settings, from brightly lighted regions to poorly lit storage zones. Because of this, the sensors and cameras on the AGV need to be able to perform correctly in a variety of illumination scenarios. Particularly in places like cold storage facilities or outside, temperature and humidity levels can vary greatly. In both working environments, the coverage of wireless networks has been greatly improved. Clear requirements are established, which greatly facilitates the communication between the AGV and the host computer. The communication and sensor systems of the AGV may be impacted by this interference. To reduce this, the AGV has to feature EMI-resistant parts and dependable communication protocols that guarantee continuous functioning even when high electromagnetic fields are present. Regulations and safety requirements unique to the AGV's operating environment must be followed. To safeguard both the AGV and the human workers engaging with it, this entails having emergency stop mechanisms, warning signs, and approval from workplace safety standards.

Selecting the wheel train structure and AGV driving mode

Drive mode: An Automated Guided Vehicle's (AGV) maneuverability, load-carrying capacity, and overall operating efficiency are largely determined by its driving mode and wheel train configuration. The driving mode and wheel train construction must be carefully chosen to create an AGV with specified specifications, such as a load capacity of 400 kg and a minimum turning radius of 650mm.

Differential drive: Differential drive, a popular drive mode in AGV designs because of its ease of use and efficiency in obtaining precise control, has been selected for this particular AGV. When using differential drive, the AGV's two independently controlled drive wheels are paired with one or more caster wheels for stability. By adjusting the drive wheels' speed and direction, this setup enables the AGV to do abrupt maneuvers, even rotating on the spot. An important characteristic for maneuvering in confined places in industrial settings is the AGV's ability to turn in situ by rotating one wheel forward and the other backward. Improved agility and precise control are two benefits of the differential drive mode that are crucial for negotiating intricate routes and dodging obstructions. Furthermore, it lowers the number of moving components and streamlines the mechanical design, increasing dependability and requiring less maintenance. The use of DC motors with high torque and reduction gearboxes guarantees the AGV's ability to operate smoothly and precisely even under enormous loads.

A single steering wheel: A single steering wheel AGV is quite easy to use, which is similar to how a double steering wheel AGV is controlled using a driving wheel. On the other hand, as compared to a single steering wheel AGV, the rear wheel functions as a follower, therefore the matter of the motors' collaboration is not relevant. Just a few fundamental controls may be finished, and just one steering wheel can produce a single steering wheel driving action. Moreover, the caster wheels are essential for preserving equilibrium and enabling fluid motion. Strategically positioned in the corners of the AGV, they support a portion of the weight and enhance stability, preventing tipping when turning, accelerating, and decelerating. Because the caster wheels may freely rotate, they can align with the direction of motion and provide less resistance, which makes navigation easier and keeps the drive wheels from wearing down. In order to guarantee longevity and functionality, the wheels' material selection is essential. Usually composed of premium rubber or polyurethane, the drive wheels provide excellent traction and durability. In order to endure constant use in industrial settings, the caster wheels are also composed of sturdy materials. To sum up, the differential drive mode, when paired with a well-thought-out wheel train layout, gives the AGV the stability, maneuverability, and load-handling capacity it needs to operate effectively in industrial environments. With careful selection of reduction gearboxes, drive motors, and wheel materials, the AGV can manage large loads, maneuver through challenging conditions, and operate

dependably with little maintenance. Achieving the required operating efficiency and effectiveness of the AGV requires an integrated approach to the selection of the drive mode and wheel train arrangement.

The arrangement of the gear train: There are the following functional types of wheels: the driving wheel, movable wheel, and fixed wheel are all crucial components of the gear train configuration for the AGV drive system.

Driving Wheel: The wheel that provides driving force for the AGV. There are individual steering wheels and driving wheels used in pairs. The driving wheel is usually connected to the motor through a reduction mechanism. The speed of the driving wheel is determined by the motor output speed and deceleration. The transmission reduction ratio of the machine is determined, and the speed of the driving wheel determines the driving speed of the AGV. Usually having a bigger diameter than the other wheels, the driving wheel can provide the AGV enough traction and torque to drive, especially when it is hauling high loads. Its surface frequently has grooves or patterns to increase grip on different types of flooring, guaranteeing steady and fluid movement even in difficult situations.

Movable Wheel: Also called universal wheel, it refers to a caster whose caster bracket can rotate in all directions. This type of wheel enables the AGV to steer and support the body, and is usually installed in front of the AGV. It may spin freely in any direction. The AGV can swiftly change directions without slipping or skidding thanks to its swiveling motion, which guarantees accurate and fluid movements in small areas. The movable wheel lessens the strain on the driving wheel and increases overall traction and stability by supporting a portion of the AGV's weight and absorbing lateral stresses during turns. Its design usually consists of a ball-bearing swivel mechanism housed in a sturdy casing, which allows for smooth rotation and long-term dependability in harsh industrial settings.

Fixed Wheel: The fixed wheel, often referred to as the support wheel or stabilizing wheel, gives the AGV's chassis extra stability and support, particularly when it accelerates, decelerates, or makes abrupt direction changes. The fixed wheel, in contrast to the movable wheel, is immobile and supports the weight of the AGV, preventing it from tipping or tilting while in use. The fixed wheel, which is positioned at the other end of the AGV from the movable wheel, equally distributes weight throughout the chassis to provide balanced load distribution and reduce the possibility of instability. Its sturdy wheel hub is firmly fixed to the chassis frame, and a premium bearing assembly reduces friction and guarantees smooth spinning. The sturdy construction and stable arrangement of the fixed wheel make it perfect for adding extra stability and support, particularly in AGVs transporting hefty or uneven loads.

Fig. 3: Two-wheel differential gear train distribution model

The dependability of the AGV walking route is given top priority in the gear train arrangement for AGV type A. It is necessary to carefully examine pressure bearing during the design phase of this four-wheel AGV since its differential structure is designed to directly carry the pressure from the AGV and the load above the vehicle body. This kind of AGV is frequently utilized in one-way operating situations with simple and dependable navigation, sometimes making utilization of several wheel train distribution arrangements to guarantee stability and fluid movement. The two

moveable wheels of an AGV type B are essential for steering the vehicle and supporting its body, while the two fixed wheels guarantee the stability of the AGV's motion. The driving wheel of type B, in contrast to type A, is not directly under pressure from the AGV and the load, which may prolong the drive structure's useful life. But in order to deal with problems like wheel slippage, this differential drive arrangement usually needs shock absorption capability. One-way walking situations are typical uses for AGVs with type B gear train distribution, whose control scheme is quite similar to type A. For both AGV types, efficiency, stability, and dependability are given top priority in the gear train arrangement. With careful consideration given to pressure bearing, shock absorption, and steering control, each kind meets certain operating requirements and navigational obstacles. These gear train arrangements enhance AGVs' overall efficiency and performance in industrial settings.

There is another situation in the gear train layout for AGV type A, the reliability of the AGV walking path is prioritized. The differential structure of this four-wheel AGV is designed to directly bear the pressure from the AGV and the load above the vehicle body, necessitating careful consideration of pressure bearing during the design phase. This type of AGV is commonly used in one-way operation scenarios where the navigation method is straightforward and reliable, often employing a large number of wheel train distribution structures to ensure stability and smooth movement. For both types of AGVs, efficiency, stability, and dependability are given top priority in the gear train arrangement. Each variety takes particular operating needs and navigational difficulties into account, paying close attention to steering control, shock absorption, and pressure bearing. The overall efficiency and performance of AGVs in industrial settings are enhanced by these gear train arrangements. Furthermore, AGV type's differential structure—which has fixed drive wheels—ensures steadiness when operating. With the exception of allowing bi-directional motion due to the use of a universal wheel construction for all four driven wheels, this structure has many of the same benefits as type B.

Control mode selection: As control mode selection directly affects the efficiency, dependability, and flexibility of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) in diverse industrial situations, it is a crucial design consideration. Depending on the operating requirements, task complexity, and environmental factors, one might choose to use an industrial computer, a microcontroller, or a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC). There are certain advantages and difficulties associated with each of these controllers that should be properly evaluated.

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs): If it is an AGV car with magnetic navigation or QR code navigation, PLC can complete positioning and navigation control; if it is an AGV product with laser/natural contour navigation, ordinary PLC products cannot adapt, and you need to develop related products yourself or purchase a laser navigation module. The motion control of the turbine is completed by the MC module on the PLC, and supports secondary packaging development. Compared with PLC, the advantage of industrial computers lies in the flexibility of its operating system and richer peripheral and interface resources. At the same time, the rich built-in resources and powerful data computing power also make the industrial computer functions more complete

Benefits:

Dependability: PLCs are made to operate continuously and with great dependability in industrial settings. Their ability to tolerate severe circumstances including high heat, dust, and vibrations makes them perfect for AGV applications in manufacturing facilities and storage facilities.

Programming is simple for PLCs as they employ functional block diagrams or ladder logic, which are well-known to professionals that work in industrial automation. Programming is so simple that adjustments and troubleshooting may be done quickly.

Integration: PLCs can easily integrate with various industrial sensors and actuators, enabling seamless control of the AGV's navigation, loading, and unloading operations.

Safety and Standards: PLCs are built to meet stringent industrial safety standards, ensuring safe operation of AGVs.

Difficulties:

Cost: Because PLCs have more capabilities and industrial-grade components than microcontrollers, they might be more expensive.

Limited Processing Power: PLCs may not be able to do particularly sophisticated calculations or real-time data processing jobs as well as industrial computers, despite being appropriate for many control tasks.

Scalability: Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) are often engineered to do certain jobs; to handle more complicated or diverse activities, they may need extra modules or upgrades, which can raise the total cost and complexity.

Fig. 4: Controlling AGV with PLC

Industrial Computers: The major component of an AGV's hardware, industrial computers offer the flexibility and strong processing capacity needed to manage intricate control algorithms and data processing jobs.

Perks:

Processing Power: Because industrial computers have more processing power than personal computers, they can handle more complicated tasks including data analysis, picture processing, and real-time navigation. Because of this, they are perfect for AGVs working in dynamic and unexpected situations.

Flexibility: They allow for the development and deployment of control software in a number of programming languages and run a range of operating systems. This enables interaction with different software tools and the use of sophisticated control algorithms.

Networking: Industrial computers have several networking choices, such as Ethernet, USB, and wireless interfaces, which make it easier to communicate with sensors, other systems, and the cloud. Real-time monitoring and the implementation of IoT solutions depend on this connectivity.

Ample memory and storage are provided, which are necessary for executing sophisticated simulations, storing operational data, and enabling cutting-edge machine learning techniques.

Problems:

Cost and Complexity: Compared to PLCs and microcontrollers, industrial computers are often more costly and difficult to set up and maintain.

Environmental Sensitivity: In particularly hostile situations, they are usually less resilient than PLCs, despite their ruggedness. It might be necessary to take extra precautions to guarantee dependable operation.

Power Consumption: They use more energy, which may be problematic for AGVs that run on batteries. Battery life and optimal performance are dependent on effective power management techniques.

Fig. 5: Controlling AGV with industrial computer.

Microcontrollers: Frequently used in smaller AGV systems, microcontrollers are tiny, reasonably priced controllers that work well for basic control applications.

Benefits:

Cost-Effective: Microcontrollers are an affordable option for more straightforward AGV applications since they are substantially less expensive than PLCs and industrial computers.

Low Power Consumption: They use less power, which is good since it prolongs the operating time between battery charges for AGVs that run on batteries.

Simplicity: Microcontrollers are easy to program in assembly or C, making them ideal for basic control tasks. Because of their simplicity, they are perfect for simple applications like motor control and simple navigation.

Compact Size: They are appropriate for situations where space is limited because of their tiny size, which makes it simple to integrate them into compact AGV designs.

Difficulties:

Limited processing capacity: Microcontrollers are not capable of handling massive datasets, sophisticated navigation algorithms, or complicated activities requiring a lot of computing power. Simple, repetitive control activities are best suited for them.

Restricted Connectivity: In general, they have fewer connectivity choices than industrial computers, which may limit their ability to integrate with cutting-edge sensors and communication networks.

Scalability: Industrial computers and PLCs are more scalable than microcontrollers. It is generally a control board built based on a chip or core board as a controller and an external circuit developed by yourself. Because the control methods of PLC and industrial computers are not only much more expensive than microcontrollers in terms of controllers, but also the matching modules and actuators are usually much more expensive than the supporting facilities of microcontrollers.

Fig. 6: Controlling AGV with Microchip

Optimal control mode selection for fixed production processes is best demonstrated by the DMN2000-D226 AGV logistics vehicle, which is employed in a variety of sectors including publishing and printing, home appliances, electronics, tobacco, pharmaceuticals, and autos. It was found that the DMN2000-D226's operating environment did not require such sophisticated capabilities, despite the device being first examined for integration with the flexible but expensive NDC control system. Rather, because of its dependability, simplicity, and affordability, a single-chip microcontroller control approach was selected. Because they are far less expensive than sophisticated control systems, microcontrollers are suitable for routine, repeated operations that are frequently found in stationary manufacturing lines. They minimize downtime with their reliable and steady functioning. The microcontroller method is ideally suited to meet the demand for dependable, reasonably priced solutions when combined with magnetic navigation, which guarantees excellent positional accuracy, ease of use, and economy. This tactical choice guarantees that the DMN2000-D226 can effectively fulfil job requirements, optimizing material handling and logistics operations while avoiding needless costs.

Mechanical Part Design

AGV Performance Requirements: Navigation method: magnetic navigation, Load: 400kg, Minimum turning radius: 650mm, Navigation and positioning requirements: ± 10mm, Drive mode: differential drive.

Selection of driving wheel: For the 400 kg load-carrying AGV, factors such as load capacity, material, traction, size, motor compatibility, durability, and environmental conditions must be considered while choosing the driving wheel. The combination of longevity and grip on smooth industrial surfaces makes polyurethane wheels perfect. To ensure effective functioning and maneuverability, the wheel size must correspond with the torque and speed requirements of the motor. To guarantee long-lasting performance, maintenance and environmental conditions like temperature and chemical exposure should be considered. In tough industrial situations, our all-inclusive strategy ensures dependable and effective AGV performance.

Estimating the car body load: To guarantee that an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) can transport the necessary weight effectively and securely, estimating the vehicle body load is essential during the design process. In this procedure, the weight of the payload the AGV will convey as well as its own weight must be calculated to determine the total load it will support. The aluminum alloy casing and steel chassis are the intended materials. Aluminum alloy has a density of 2.7×kg/m³, while steel has a density of 7.85×kg/m³. The AGV chassis and frame weight roughly equals to.

We know that,

$$M_s = \rho \times L \times b \times h \tag{3.1}$$

$$M_s = \rho_1 L_1 b_1 h_1 + \rho_2 L_2 b_2 h_2 + \rho_3 (L_3 b_3 h_3 + L_4 b_4 h_4) \times 2 \tag{3.2}$$

$$M_s = 7.85 \times 10^3 \times 1.5 \times 0.3 \times 0.005 + 2.7 \times 10^3 \times 1.5 \times 0.3 \times 0.002 + 2.7 \times 1.5 \times 0.4 \times 0.002 + 0.7 \times 0.4 \times 0.002 \times 2$$

$$M_s = 30\text{kg}$$

The driving wheels are 5 kg×2, the driven wheels are 3 kg×4, and the lifting mechanism weight around 40 kg. The initial batteries weight selection was 15.95 kg.

Required Load $M_f = 400\text{kg}$

Therefore, the trolley load

$$M = 400 + 30 + 15.95 + 5 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 + 40 = 505.2\text{kg}$$

505.2 kg is the estimated total weight for the AGV, including the trolley load. Both the cargo that the AGV is intended to deliver and its own self-weight are taken into account in this thorough load calculation. It is crucial to make sure the AGV can manage this load securely and effectively. It is possible to optimize the AGV for dependable and strong performance by taking into account elements like weight capacity, material durability, and environmental

circumstances. The anticipated load further emphasizes how crucial it is to choose the right parts, including the driving wheel and engine, in order to preserve stability and effectiveness when operating.

Driving wheel selection: The choosing procedure necessitates the consideration of several important variables. The AGV's driving wheel needs to be strong enough to sustain both the vehicle's own weight and any additional cargo it plans to deliver. For a wheel to operate safely and effectively, it must be able to support the anticipated weight without buckling or failing. Steel, rubber, and polyurethane are often used materials for driving wheels. Every material has distinct benefits and qualities. Those are very resilient, wear-resistant, and durable, making them appropriate for a variety of uses. Although they may wear out more rapidly, rubber wheels offer good grip on uneven ground and stress absorption. Although steel wheels can cause damage to flooring and need additional traction upgrades, they are incredibly robust and appropriate for heavy-duty applications. Now examine the wheel load and size of the trolley. Hanke Company's AGV-ALB295A-P53-140/34/50 is chosen to be the driving wheel. These are its parameters from AutoCAD design:

Table 1: Driving wheel parameters

Wheel diameter D (mm)	Wheel width T2 (mm)	Load (kg) at 4.5km/h
140	34	350
Hub groove width (B) (mm)	Hub groove height (H) (mm)	
8	15.8	
Shaft hole diameter d (mm)	Wheelbase length (T1) (mm)	
19.6	32	

Fig. 7: driving wheel structure's Schematic diagram

Selection of driving motor: The power needs, torque, motor type, efficiency, size, compatibility with control systems, environmental issues, and dependability must all be carefully taken into account when choosing the driving motor for your AGV. It is crucial to compute the power required to move the AGV while accounting for its overall weight and intended speed. Determining the required torque also guarantees maneuverability and smooth acceleration. The choice of motor relies on the particulars of the application; brushed DC and servo motors are two examples of available possibilities, and each has advantages of its own. In order to maximize energy use and extend battery life, efficiency is essential. AGV design ensures smooth integration with size and weight constraints. Additional factors influencing motor selection include environmental resilience and control system compatibility. In the end, choosing reliable

products from recognized manufacturers guarantees constant performance and reduces the need for maintenance, which enables the AGV to operate successfully in a variety of industrial settings.

Running resistance calculation: To calculate the force needed to move an AGV through its operating environment, running resistance must be taken into account. Considerations include air resistance, rolling resistance, gravitational force, and frictional losses. The force needed to overcome ground friction is accounted for by rolling resistance, which is determined by several factors such as the surface quality and material of the wheels. The force that opposes the AGV's forward motion is air resistance, which depends on its speed and frontal area. Resistance to going uphill or downhill is influenced by variations in elevation and gravitational force. Running resistance is further influenced by frictional losses, such as those resulting from drivetrain and bearing components. Engineers can assure effective and dependable functioning in a range of operating circumstances by designing AGVs with the right power and torque parameters by precisely calculating these factors.

Static friction for AGVs

$$F_f = \mu F_n \tag{3.3}$$

Where,

The static friction force is denoted by F_f .

Coefficient of friction (μ) is 0.1.

The normal force is calculated by multiplying the mass (505.2kg) by the acceleration caused by gravity (9.8 m/s²).

$$F_f = 0.1 \times 505.2\text{kg} \times 9.8\text{m/s}^2 = 495.1\text{N}$$

Using the coefficient of friction (0.1) and the normal force applied by the vehicle's load (505.2 kg), the static friction force for the AGV is determined to be 495.15 Newton. This number is essential for figuring out how much power and torque the AGV will need to get over its first resistance and operate without a hitch in the desired environment.

Resistance to acceleration: Here for the AGV the speed is 30m/min when it crossed the 1m distance. So, the acceleration the AGV encounters over a distance of one meter when it achieves a speed of thirty meters per minute (0.5 meters per second) must be calculated in order to establish the resistance to acceleration. The kinematic equation for evenly accelerated motion is used in this situation. The formula is:

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2as \tag{3.4}$$

Where:

The ultimate velocity, v , is equal to 0.5 m/s.

The starting velocity, denoted as u , is set to 0 m/s, assuming the AGV begins at rest.

The acceleration is denoted by a

The distance is denoted by s (1 m)

$$a = \frac{v^2 - u^2}{2s} = \frac{(0.5\text{m/s})^2 - (0\text{m/s})^2}{2 \times 1\text{m}} = 0.125\text{m/s}^2$$

We apply Newton's second rule of motion, which states that force equals the product of mass and acceleration, to calculate the force needed to accelerate the AGV. Considering that the AGV's mass (M) is 505.2 kg and its computed acceleration

Since $a = 0.125 \text{ m/s}^2$, we can calculate the force F_j using the following method:

$$F_j = M \times a$$

$$F_j = 63.1\text{N}$$

The AGV has to accelerate by 63.1 Newton to reach a speed of 30 meters per minute over a distance of one meter. When constructing the AGV's drive system, this force—which stands for the resistance to acceleration—is crucial to ensuring that the system can accomplish the required performance within its operating constraints.

In order to ascertain the overall running resistance of the AGV, we amalgamate the force of static friction (F_f) and the acceleration force (F_j) needed for the move.

$$F_f = 495.1\text{N and } F_j = 63.16\text{N}$$

The total running resistance

$$F = 495.15\text{N} + 63.16\text{N} = 558.3\text{N}$$

The AGV has a total running resistance of 558.3 Newton. The drive system's design must take into account this overall resistance in order to guarantee that the motor and control systems can overcome it and continue to operate dependably and efficiently.

Selection of Drive motor: Choosing the right drive motor for an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) is a careful procedure that guarantees the vehicle satisfies performance standards while preserving dependability and efficiency. AGVs that are intended to carry weights up to 400 kg with a minimum turning radius of 650 mm and at speeds up to 4.5 km/h require careful consideration of a number of criteria when choosing their motors.

Minimum Power and Torque Needed: Assuring that a drive motor has sufficient power and torque is the main consideration. In order to overcome the AGV's overall running resistance—which consists of both static friction and the force needed for acceleration—the motor must provide adequate torque. The motor must also continue to operate consistently in order to guarantee dependable and seamless functioning. One important factor that determines the motor's capacity to manage the load and operational requirements of the AGV is the torque requirement.

Rapidity and Effectiveness: The operating requirements of the AGV must be met by the motor's speed. Because the AGV must travel at 30 meters per minute, or 0.5 meters per second, the motor needs to be able to operate steadily at this pace. The motor's efficiency is also vital as it affects the AGV's total energy usage and battery life. In industrial environments, productivity must be maintained. High-efficiency motors do this by reducing energy losses and extending operating durations between charges.

Maintain Compatibility: The chosen motor needs to work with the control system of the AGV. Since the AGV in this instance uses a microcontroller-based control system, the motor must be able to accommodate exact control signals. Microcontroller systems may be used with brushless DC motors to achieve precise speed and torque control through electronic commutation.

Trustworthiness and Manufacturer Assistance: Ultimately, the motor's dependability and the manufacturer's assistance are critical. Selecting motors from reliable suppliers that have a reputation for producing high-quality products and offering strong customer service guarantees that any problems can be fixed fast, reducing downtime.

Now the calculation part: The automated guided vehicle's (AGV) speed is 0.5 meters per second. We must enter the right values into the provided formula in order to calculate the wheel speed.

As stated:

$$\text{AGV speed: } v = 0.5 = 0.5 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Wheel diameter } D = 140 \text{ mm } (0.140 \text{ m}) = 140 D$$

$$n = \frac{30,000}{\pi \times 140} \tag{3.5}$$

$$n = \frac{30,000}{439.82} \approx 68.23 \text{ r/min}$$

With a 140 mm wheel diameter, the wheel speed ought to be around 68.23 revolutions per minute.

The characteristics of the drive wheel also have an impact on the force and speed that the drive structure can transfer, in addition to the reducer's output.

Motion resistance moment we can use the formula

$$M = F \times R \tag{3.6}$$

$$M = (558.3\text{N}) \times (0.07\text{m}) = 39.08\text{Nm}$$

Power required by the motor we can use the given formula:

$$P_{n_{total}} = \frac{1}{3600\eta} \left(m \cdot g \cdot f + \frac{C_d \cdot A \cdot V_{max}^2}{21.15} \right) \cdot V_{max} \tag{3.7}$$

Where m is the mass of the AGV (in kg), and η is the efficiency of the chosen reduction motor (0.96). The coefficient of rolling resistance is denoted by f , the drag coefficient is represented by C_d , and the acceleration due to gravity is given by g (9.8 m/s²) AGV's frontal area is denoted by A and its maximum speed by AGV is V_{max} .

$$P_{n_{total}} = \frac{1}{3456} \times 99.0977 \times 1.8 \approx 51.63\text{W} \approx 51.7\text{W}$$

Consequently, a single motor's rated power and necessary starting torque are

$$M=19.54 \text{ and } P_n=25.85\text{W}$$

When the AGV has to halt for emergency purposes, it must accelerate by a minimum of 0.05 meters while decelerating.

$$a = \frac{\bar{v}V}{s} = 2.5\text{m/s}^2 \tag{3.8}$$

Motors need a required force and that

$$F_s = aM - F_f = aM - \mu F_n = 1164.1\text{N} \tag{3.9}$$

So, for the single motor

$$F_{f1} = 582.065\text{N}$$

The total torque required for motor is

$$M_s = F_{f1}R = 582.065 \times 0.070 = 40.7\text{N} \cdot \text{M} \tag{3.10}$$

The motor is chosen based on its rated power and necessary starting torque. We have now selected Xin Yongtai, 5840-555-2480. These are its parameters.

Table 2: Driving motor parameters

Rated voltage	Power	Rated current
24V	28.8W	1.2A
Rated speed	Rated torque	Stall torque
60rpm	14.5kg·cm	58kg·cm

To properly fulfil the AGV's operating requirements, the drive motor of choice has to have a few key features. It must deliver enough torque to go past the motion resistance and guarantee the vehicle propels itself smoothly. Furthermore, the power rating of the motor need to correspond with the power needs of the AGV in order to guarantee maximum efficiency and minimal energy usage. Based on the AGV's operational parameters, such as speed, load capacity, and environmental influences, a 40.7 Nm torque output motor has been found to be appropriate. Even in the face of opposition, the torque value allows the motor to deliver the required force to propel the AGV ahead.

Fig. 8: Diagram of drive motor

Structure design of Drive wheel transmission: An essential part of an AGV's overall design is the drive wheel transmission's structural layout (Automated Guided Vehicle). The effectiveness and dependability of the AGV's movement within its operating environment is guaranteed by this system. The wheel assembly, the gear train, and the drive motor are three important components of the design. To function well together and satisfy the unique needs of the AGV, each of these parts has to be carefully developed.

Design of bearing: Double pivot points are selected for one-way fixing in this design via the bearing configuration approach. Two bearings positioned in opposition to one another, each restricting the axial movement of the shaft in a single direction, typically make up this bearing assembly. The inner and outer rings of the bearing are adjusted during assembly to regulate the axial position and enable the bearing to achieve the desired position and condition.

Calculation: Radial load

$$F_r = M/2 = 2254\text{N} \tag{3.11}$$

Axial Load let, $F_a=300\text{N}$

So
$$F_{r1} = F_{r2} = \frac{F_r}{2} = 1127\text{N} \tag{3.12}$$

Derived Axial load

Assume that an angular contact bearing with $e=0.4$ and $\alpha=15^\circ$ is used.

$$F_{d1} = F_{d2} = eF_{r1} = 611.06\text{N}$$

So, it's for bearing 1 that the derived axial load is 611.06N

And for the bearing 2 the total axial load

$$F_{a2} = F_a + F_{d1} = 911.06\text{N} \tag{3.13}$$

The equivalent dynamic load

$$P = f_d (XF_r + YF_a) \tag{3.14}$$

If we assume $f_d = 1.2$

Then for bearing 1 $e = 0.4$

So now I take $X_1 = 1, Y_1 = 0$

For bearing 2

$$P_1 = 733.278\text{N}$$

$$\frac{F_{a2}}{F_{r2}} = 0.8084 > e = 0.4$$

If we take $X_2 = 0.44, Y_2 = 1.4$

$$P_2 = 2,125.6\text{N}$$

Now we need to pick $P=P_1=2,125.6\text{N}$

Dynamic load rating

$$C = \frac{P}{f_t} \sqrt[3]{\frac{60nL_h'}{10^6}} = 9586.6\text{N} \tag{3.15}$$

So now we can select the bearing for our drawing is as 7203C

Rating of life

$$L_h = \frac{10^6}{60n} \left(\frac{C}{P}\right)^3 = 29429.8\text{h} \tag{3.16}$$

Table 3: parameters for bearing

Outer diameter	Basic dynamic load rating	Basic static load rating
46mm	10.9kN	5.9kN

The extensive assessment and selection procedure resulted in the selection of bearings that not only match but also surpass the AGV's operational specifications. With a life rating of 29,429.8 hours and a dynamic load rating of 9586.68 N, the chosen bearings guarantee the AGV's capacity to operate dependably in industrial environments, managing the recommended loads and operating conditions efficiently. This meticulous selection highlights the dedication to performance and quality, which in turn enhances the AGV's overall effectiveness, durability, and success in its intended applications.

Key selection: For an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) to function reliably and to provide rotational force without slippage, mechanical keys for parts like wheels, shafts, and gears must be chosen and verified during the design process. Whether square, rectangular, or Woodruff, the keys must be constructed of high-strength materials, and their type must correspond to the torque and load requirements of the application. Rigid verification procedures, such as fit and tolerance inspections, material testing, load testing, defect inspection, and durability testing, are crucial, as are accurate dimensions and tolerances. By confirming that the keys can withstand operational stress and maintain long-term reliability, these procedures lower the likelihood of mechanical failures and need less maintenance. This methodical procedure guarantees smooth, effective operation and increases the AGV's longevity.

Calculation

Let

Length of contact $l = 22\text{mm}$

So, the torque key can convey

$$T_s = 0.25hl^2d[F] = 190.08\text{N} \cdot \text{M} \tag{3.17}$$

Here $T_s > M_s$ so we can say that it's suitable for this

Selection of Coupling: The coupling model is XHW-44C. The parameters are

Table: 4

Nominal torque	Allowable speed	Moment of inertia
15N·M	1400r/min	0.000047kg·m ²

Fig. 9: Diagram of coupling

With the goal of maximizing dependability and performance, the XHW-44C coupling was chosen for the AGV design. The solid build, substantial torque capability, and superior alignment qualities of this particular model are what make it the choice for smooth power transfer from the motor to the drive wheels. By accommodating misalignments and absorbing shocks and vibrations, the XHW-44C provides smooth and efficient operation while minimizing wear and tear on associated components. It is a great fit for the AGV, increasing both its lifespan and operational efficiency thanks to its demonstrated robustness and performance in demanding industrial applications. Through the integration of the XHW-44C connection, we guarantee that the AGV operates consistently even under varying load situations, which eventually leads to a more dependable and maintenance-free operation.

Shaft sleeve calibration: A bushing with an inner diameter of 17 mm and a length of 4 mm is needed for the shaft assembly. Shaft sleeves are made of 45 steels, which has been quenched and tempered. The 45 steel is linked dynamically. When the outer diameter is 20 mm, the permissible compressive stress under $\sigma_p = 40\text{mpa}$

$$\sigma = \frac{F_a}{s} = 3.443\text{mpa} \tag{3.18}$$

So here $S=1.3$ and $\sigma_p > S\sigma$ therefore it can be used in AGV.

Wheel stand: Here we need to assume safety factor 1.5 and because of 45 steels $\sigma=355\text{Mpa}$

So, compressive stress of the wheel frame

$$\sigma = \frac{F_N}{A} = 4.696\text{Mpa}$$

$$[\sigma] = 355 > S\sigma = 6.1\text{Mpa}$$

Check of the top bolt connection for 4 M6 bolt is

$$F = a_{max}M = 631.56\text{N}$$

$$\sigma_1 = 2.8\text{MPa}$$

$$[\sigma_p] = \frac{\sigma_p}{s_p} = 40\text{MPa} \tag{3.19}$$

the force is not controlled under variable load, and $S=10$ is taken.

$$2.8\text{MPa} < [\tau]$$

Consequently, the extrusion strength is met.

the bolt shear strength of the jacking base plate:

$$\frac{F}{i\frac{\pi}{4}d_0^2} \leq [\tau] \quad (3.20)$$

$$\tau_1 = \frac{631.56}{4\frac{\pi}{4}0.005^2} = 8.05 \text{ MPa}$$

$$[\tau] = \frac{\sigma_s}{S_\tau} = 24 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau_2 < [\tau]$$

Shear strength is therefore satisfied. The bottom plate bolts are clearly positioned appropriately. As a result, the wheel frame has a sensible design.

Jacking device design

Drive selection: After study, there are about seven types of linear transmission mechanisms that satisfy the AGV functions described in this article.

Trapezoidal screw: The movement efficiency of the trapezoidal screw is around 30%. Because the friction mechanism is sliding friction, it creates a lot of heat during operation, making it unsuitable for high-speed applications. The sliding friction surface is severely degraded during operation, resulting in a short service life. Keep it clean and lubricated while in use. The trapezoidal screw offers strong self-locking capabilities. Processing and production are typically completed in a single step, resulting in great efficiency and cheap costs.

Ball screw: Ball screw offers less friction loss and good gearbox efficiency. Ball screws' friction shape allows for excellent motion efficiency, often ranging from 90-96%. High accuracy: Ball screws are mass-produced using high-precision machinery, resulting in high precision. Support high-speed and small feed: Because the ball screw pair has low static friction, the beginning torque is low, and crawling is rare, ensuring precise micro-feed. The ball screw cannot self-lock, although it is capable of reverse gearbox.

Electric push rod: Its features include compact size, high thrust, and powerful self-locking ability. Because it relies on a motor for power, it eliminates the requirement for air pressure, hydraulic components, and so on; nonetheless, it cannot handle radial stresses.

Electric cylinder: The electric cylinder is a systematic product that incorporates the servo motor and screw into a single unit. It has great stiffness, excellent impact resistance, and is simple to use and maintain. It has been extensively employed in industry.

Linear motor: The linear motor's simple form and low motion inertia allow it to attain high motion characteristics and positioning precision. Ordinary materials can handle faster movement speeds due to circular conversion. There is a gap between the stator and the mover, and there is no contact while the motor moves, resulting in no friction or noise and a long operating life.

Hydraulic cylinder: When used in low speed and large load circumstances, the force may reach hundreds of thousands of tones. As a result, it is widely utilized in heavy industries. Disadvantages for that maintenance is difficult since it demands strong sealing performance, and the cost is quite expensive.

The electric pushrod is used as the driving device in this article because to its high integration, compact footprint, great thrust, and excellent self-locking ability. Because it is powered by a motor, no air pressure or hydraulic components are required. As a result, the size and weight of the AGV may be minimized, and it has strong self-locking capability to assure the stability of the jacking device. However, because the electric push rod cannot handle radial loads, even if the jacking device primarily bears radial forces, it must perform axial placement and bear some radial loads. As a result, it is recommended to position the lifting plate using four linear bearings.

Electric actuator selection: According to the selection method provided by the electric push rod manufacturer, first check the working system, select the push rod type according to the working system, and then select the electric push

rod model according to the load and self-locking rate requirements and working conditions to determine the push rod stroke, and then check the stability and lifespan to determine whether a larger model of push rod needs to be selected.

Fig. 10: Working system of actuator

t2, t4, t6: working time and t1, t3, t5: waiting time So Calculation of electric push rod working system

$$F_u = \frac{(t_2+t_4+t_6)}{10} = \frac{0.5+0.5}{10} = 10\% \tag{3.21}$$

The lifting device has a working time of $F_u < 30\%$, requiring a trapezoidal screw electric actuator and LAP with high impact resistance for industrial applications. Because we employ the electric push rod as a lifting mechanism, we can determine the weight on the trolley. The jacking mechanism requires that when the motor is turned off and subjected to a force opposing the movement, such as the gravity of the trolley weight, the push rod does not move, so the self-locking coefficient be less than 0.25.

As can be seen from the above, the load requirement is 400kg, and assume that the life requirement is $h=20,000$ hours. According to the manufacturer's specifications, the LAP25 has a thrust of 1 ton with a DC 24V motor, allowing it to satisfy the load's lifting requirements. The electric actuator data is shown below:

Table 5: Lap25 motor's parameter

Model	Speed	Dynamic load
LAP25	7mm/s	3000N
Self-locking coefficient	Motor parameters	Rated current
0.17	DC24V	9.5A
Reduction ratio	Weight	Weight per 100mm stroke
L1	3.2kg	0.4kg

Life check: The working life of an electric actuator is determined by the component with the shortest life among its components. Therefore, we mainly check the working life of the screw part. Although the worm gear part will also wear out with work, its service life is still longer than that of the screw.

$$L = \left(\frac{c}{F_m}\right) S = 75km \tag{3.22}$$

Assuming 10 lifts per hour:

$$L_1 = hSn = 20km(3).$$

$$L > L_1$$

So, we can say it's suitable

Linear bearing selection: The required acceleration when the car moves forward is 0.125. When the car requires an emergency stop, the acceleration is 2.5

F_a : The force that provides the load acceleration of the car

$$F_a = ma = 1000N \quad (3.23)$$

$$F_1 = F_a/4 = 250N \quad (3.24)$$

A double-lined linear bearing must be able to sustain a specific level of torque.

The optical axis measures 225mm in length. The moment when the bearing is most stressed is when the shaft segment is 60mm in the bearing.

$$F = \frac{F_a \times l}{l_1} = \frac{250 \times 0.16}{0.06} = 666.7N \quad (3.25)$$

Therefore, the force on the linear bearing is approximately

$$F_m = 2F - F_a = 1082N \quad (3.26)$$

The moment is

$$T = FL = 250 \times 0.225 = 56.25N \cdot M \quad (3.27)$$

Since the linear bearing works under impact load, the static strength safety factor is 1.3

According to

$$C_0 \geq S_0 P_0 = 1406.6 \quad (3.28)$$

Therefore, LML11 D30 linear bearing can be selected.

Linear bearing life check

$$L_h = \frac{10^6 a_1}{60n} \left(\frac{C}{P} \right)^\varepsilon = 21772h \quad (3.29)$$

The dependability is estimated at 95%. As a result, since the load collection situation is determined by the AGV acceleration, n is set to 50 based on the actual operating conditions. $a_1=0.5$

$$L_h > L'_h$$

So, it is suitable.

Battery Case Design: The batteries weight is 14.6kg, and the estimated total weight of the battery and box is 20kg. Bolt check. Since the battery box bolts are not mainly designed to bear tensile force, they are mainly checked for shear force.

Check the bolt extrusion strength of the battery box:

$$\sigma_p = \frac{F}{i d_0 L_{min}} \leq [\sigma_p] \quad (3.30)$$

$$F_t = 50N$$

$$\sigma_1 = 0.167MPa$$

$$[\sigma_p] = \frac{\sigma_p}{S_p} = 40MPa \quad (3.31)$$

Assume that the bolt condition is that the retightening force is not controlled under variable load, and $S=10$ is taken.

$$\sigma_1 = 0.167MPa < [\tau]$$

Therefore, the extrusion strength is satisfied.

Check the bolt shear strength of the battery box:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\frac{\pi}{4} d_0^2} \leq [\tau] \quad (3.32)$$

$$\tau_2 = \frac{50}{\frac{\pi}{4} 0.005^2} = 0.637MPa$$

$$[\tau] = \frac{\sigma_s}{S_\tau} = 24MPa$$

S Same as above.

From the above formula:

$$\tau_2 = 0.637\text{MPa} < [\tau]$$

Therefore, the shear strength is satisfied.

It can be seen that the bottom plate bolts are set reasonably

Anti-collision device: As the anti-collision device, select the model YC-AP006. It can not only function as an anti-collision buffer, but it can also communicate a switching value to the safety edge switch when the contact force reaches a particular threshold. For emergency processing by the controller.

The safety edge is a flexible, bendable strip. The safety edge is often put along the edge of the mechanical equipment. When it gets a specific pressure value, it generates a switch signal. The construction is made up of an aluminum alloy bracket, a rubber buffer belt, signal sensor components, and an electronic controller.

Anti-collision strip the parameters are as shown in the table:

Table 6: Parameters for buffer zone

Control level	Use with controller to achieve level 3
Protection level	IP65
ambient temperature	-20°C to 80°C
Response time	Less than 30ms
Activation intensity	>150N
Service life	100,000 times

Chassis Design: The AGV chassis is constructed from 5mm Q345 steel plate. The chassis' strength should be evaluated based on its risky areas. After stress analysis, inspect the following risky sections: the connection surface between the driving wheel support and chassis, and the connection surface between the jacking bottom plate and the chassis. Next, we'll do a shear stress test on these two risky parts. If both sides satisfy the standards, the stress on the base plate is manageable.

Connection surface between drive wheel support and chassis: It can be seen from the previous article that the load of a single driving wheel is 230kg, so the pressure of the support on the chassis is:

$$F_1 = Mg = 2254\text{N} \tag{3.33}$$

$$A = 7 \times 5 \times 2 = 70\text{mm}^2$$

Therefore, the shear stress on the dangerous section should be:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{A} = 32.2\text{MPa} \tag{3.34}$$

$$[\tau] = \frac{\sigma_s}{S} = \frac{220}{1.3} = 169.2\text{MPa}$$

Since the action form of this load is static load, the safety factor is taken as 1.3.

$$\tau \leq [\tau]$$

Therefore, the shear strength of the dangerous section is sufficient.

Lift bottom plate and chassis connection surface: As can be seen from the previous article, the load of the jacking device is 400kg, so the pressure of the support on the chassis is:

$$F_1 = Mg = 3920N$$

$$A = 4470 \times 5 = 22350\text{mm}^2$$

Therefore, the shear stress on the dangerous section should be:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{A} = 0.1\text{MPa}$$

It can be seen from the above calculation that

$$[\tau] = 169.2\text{MPa}$$

$$\tau \leq [\tau]$$

Therefore, the shear strength of the dangerous section is sufficient

Schematic diagram of Lift-up AGV: The lift-up AGV's schematic diagram showcases the vehicle's functioning and design by showing the main parts and how they work together. The central component is the chassis, which is 1500 mm long overall and is made of high-strength steel (Q345) for support and stability. The lifting mechanism includes four linear bearing bases that provide stability and smooth elevation, as well as a jacking structure driven by a Limetech push rod motor (model LAP25), which is necessary for raising large instruments. The drive system consists of four small caster wheels that improve agility and allow for smooth direction changes, as well as two larger wheels driven by reduction motors for propulsion. Numerous sensors for position tracking and obstacle identification are part of integrated navigation and control systems, which are backed by a crystal oscillator circuit for accurate timing and synchronization of onboard systems. To enable prompt stopping in an emergency, an emergency stop switch is positioned in a visible location. The AGV also contains two small, energy-efficient batteries that are simple to maintain and replace. These batteries allow for prolonged operation. Durability is improved across a range of operating circumstances by safety measures such as strengthened construction and corrosion-resistant coatings. All things considered, the schematic provides a visual depiction of the lift-up AGV, illustrating how each part is integrated to attain dependability, safety, and operating efficiency.

Fig. 11: Schematic 2D View

Hardware Design

Overall design of electrical part: As can be seen from the previous article, this article uses a single-chip microcomputer as the controller, which is smaller and cheaper than PLC and industrial computer. To complete the control of the AGV system, in addition to the controller, we also need various data collection and processing, motor driving, and voltage conversion components. Next, we propose an overall control plan for the realization of the AGV function.

Data collection and transmission part: To complete the car's navigation, obstacle avoidance, and autonomous charging features, as well as ensuring navigation reliability and safety, the following hardware equipment is necessary for data gathering and transmission:

Magnetic Navigation Sensor: Direct the AGV to follow the predefined path on the ground. Install the magnetic navigation sensor at a specific distance from the magnetic strip on the front of the vehicle. The magnetic navigation sensor contains numerous measuring locations. The measurement points can show if the magnetic field strength above the magnetic strip exceeds the threshold detected by the magnetic navigation sensor. Each point has the ability to output a switching value to the controller via the relevant port. Using the switching value of several outputs, the distribution of measurement points relative to the magnetic strip within a specific range may be determined. The deviation of the AGV is calculated based on the output switching value, and the AGV makes the appropriate control.

FRID card reader: When the AGV is required to complete the corresponding function at the corresponding location, we use FRID electronic tags to transmit high-frequency signals. When the AGV receives the corresponding high-frequency signal through the card reader, it reads the corresponding action command for implementation and transmits it through Bluetooth communication. The position information of the car is sent to the host computer, which then gives corresponding start and stop instructions and path planning.

Fig. 12: Module of FRID card reading

Ultrasonic sensor: In order to complete the detection of obstacles, we tentatively designate ultrasonic sensors as obstacle detection components. The detection distance of HCSR-04 is 2-450mm, and the sensing angle is 15°, which is enough to meet the obstacle avoidance requirements of the car. Here we use HCSR-04 for obstacle avoidance

Overall control framework: The microcontroller is used as a microcontroller to process the signals output by various sensors. The PWM wave and various electrical signals are output to realize various functions of the AGV. The movement state of the AGV is controlled by controlling the driving wheel motor to complete various corresponding requirements. Therefore, the walking function of the AGV can be obtained. Overall framework of the control system:

Fig. 13: The control structure diagram of AGV

Close loop diagram for AGV:

Fig. 14: Close loop for motion control of AGV

SCM selection

Option 1: Use the conventional 89C51 chip as the AGV control chip. Although the 51 microcontroller has the advantages of being cheap and easy to use. However, its computing power is relatively weak, its functions are relatively simple, and its internal resources are relatively insufficient. If you want to complete various control tasks for the AGV, you must expand its functions through external chips, which will make the phase control circuit bloated and cumbersome.

Option 2: C8051F005 microcontroller, as a high-performance 51 microcontroller, is enough to undertake the task of controlling AGV. This series of MCUs is fully compatible with conventional 89C51 microcontroller instructions on the system. Contains a 12-bit precision ADC module, which can be used to detect the power supply voltage in this article. Because it uses parallel pipeline operations of instructions to complete the instruction fetch-execution process, it is much faster than the standard 51 series microcontroller. Moreover, the microcontroller is easy to operate and debug, which is in line with the requirements of this design for the controller.

Based on the above analysis, option 2 is selected.

In order to ensure that the microcontroller can complete the control tasks of the AGV system. To determine whether there are enough IO ports and whether the number of communication ports can meet the requirements, you need to allocate chip pin resources first.

The following figure shows the pin resource distribution diagram of C8051F005:

Fig. 15: Pin allocation

Table 7: Function allocation Table

Pin name	Function
P0	for USRT communications
P1	Enter Magnetic Navigation Sensor
P2.0~5	Output drive wheel DC drive
P2.6	Sound and light alarm output
P3.0~3.2	Output electric actuator DC drive
P3.3~3.6	Safety edge switch input
AIN0	Input power supply voltage detection circuit

It can be seen that the C8051 microcontroller can meet the system functional requirements.

Microcontroller minimum system: The minimum system of a microcontroller usually consists of clock, reset, download and power circuits. Since the control chip is loaded onto the PCB after debugging is completed, the corresponding parts are not required. The MCU power circuit part is unified in the subsequent power system design, so this part is mainly focused on the first two circuits.

Clock circuit: The XTAL and EXTAL pins are the output and input ports of the oscillator respectively, and are generally used 12MHz crystal oscillator around MHz when wiring, you should pay attention to the fact that the high-frequency signal of the crystal oscillator will interfere with the circuits near it, so the shorter the connection between the crystal oscillator

and the main chip, the better. It is best not to wire it around the front, rear, left, and right. Two capacitors provide stability.

Reset circuit: The function of the reset circuit is as an external reset button. When errors and abnormal conditions occur due to interference during use, the reset button can be used to re-execute the internal program. When the switch is pressed, because the capacitor voltage cannot change suddenly, the voltage after power is still maintained at 0V. The voltage across the capacitor then increases over time, when the voltage is in a low state. The microcontroller is in reset state and will start working normally after reaching the high level. Since the C8051F series microcontroller is a low-level reset, the reset port of the microcontroller can perform a reset operation when it receives a low level of more than two clocks. By selecting the appropriate resistor and capacitor values, this can be achieved that lasts for more than two clock cycles. Low level to achieve the effect of microcontroller reset.

Fig. 16: reset circuit

The microcontroller reset requires a low level of $2\mu\text{s}$, so it is required:

$$T = RC > 2\mu\text{s} \tag{4.1}$$

$$T = 3 \times 10^3 \times 1 \times 10^{-6} = 3\mu\text{s}$$

Therefore, the requirement is met.

Driving wheel Dc driver: The microcontroller's electrical properties prevent it from directly driving high-power motors. As a result, it requires external power to function. The motor drive module's job is to regulate the rotation of the AGV's drive wheel using the output electrical signal from the drive chip. The motor is typically powered by an H-bridge circuit. Although the H-bridge circuit has numerous advantages, the actual design process is difficult owing to the vast number of components utilized, which complicates the circuit design significantly. As a result, we often drive motors with integrated circuits that include an H-bridge chip.

The driving wheel DC motor's rated voltage is 24V. As a result, L293E was chosen as the driver chip.

Table 8: Driver chip parameters

Operating Voltage	5~36V
Peak current	2A
Working current	1.2A
Rated power	36W

Its internal circuit includes two H-bridge drivers that can power inductive loads including DC motors, stepper motors, and relay coils. The speed may be changed by inputting PWM waves; it contains two enable connections that switch the matching working sections. Logical input terminal.

Fig. 17: Driver Chip circuit

Electric actuator DC drive: Because the electric actuators rated voltage is 24V and its operating current is 9.5A. Because general driver chips cannot support such a high current motor, a dedicated DC motor speed regulator is necessary to power it.

The speed regulator is chosen based on its driving current, and the specifications are as follows.

Table 9: Parameters of electric push rod

Supply voltage	DC 6V-36V
Rated current	12A
Control signal high level voltage	2.0V~5.5V, compatible with 3.3V and 5VTTL levels
Control signal low level voltage	0V~0.8V, 0V when floating
control signal current	50uA
PWM range	0.1%~100.0%
PWM signal frequency range	0~100KHz (recommended 20KHz)
Operating temperature	-25C-80°C
Product Size	55* 55*25mm

Heat dissipation treatment: This driver does not require heat dissipation considerations when operating in a 12A circuit. (A thin thermal conductive sheet can be placed under the driver) When the current value reaches about 15A, a heat dissipation treatment is required. In the 20A circuit, emphasis must be placed on heat dissipation.

Fig 18: Speed regulator and speed controller circuit

Magnetic navigation sensor: The magnetic navigation sensor uses PaPaYea's 8-bit magnetic navigation sensor. The magnetic sensor is distributed at 8 points, with a spacing of 10mm, and a switching transistor OC gate output, which can be connected to a PLC or MCU. The following are the sensor parameters:

Table10: Parameters of magnetic navigation sensor

Supply voltage range	DC10 to 30V
Maximum current consumption	55 mA
Output electrical mode	OC gate, NPN open collector output, conducts to ground when a valid signal is detected
Number of output channels	8 channels, N pole detection
Output switching current	50 mA max
Maximum on-voltage	Maximum 0.6V
Detection sensitivity	0.5MT
Detect effective distance	5 to 60mm
Recommended installation distance	20 to 40mm
Applicable temperature range	-10 to 50°C
responding speed	1ms

As can be seen from the above table, the detection sensitivity of the sensor is 0.5MT, that is, when the corresponding detection point of the magnetic navigation sensor is in a magnetic field greater than 0.5MT.

The magnetic navigation sensor is installed at a height of 20mm, and the 0.5MT is between 15 and 20mm, the position information of the AGV body can be ensured through the output of channels 2 and 3 and the output of channels 6 and 7. Therefore, the combination of the magnetic navigation sensor and the magnetic strip can ensure that the AGV navigation and positioning error is less than 10mm, meeting the requirements for AGV positioning accuracy.

Fig 19: Magnetic Navigation Circuit

FRID Sensor: The JY-L8900 series is developed based on radio frequency identification technology. The card reader specially designed for AGV has strong applicability. The card reader has integrated communication protocols related to the radio frequency part. It saves users the trouble of understanding and designing complex communication protocols. The card reader power supply has the ability to automatically adjust the relevant parameters of the circuit when operating in different environments, reducing the impact of the external environment on card reading. It further enhances its resistance to noise and has the characteristics of high receiving sensitivity, stable function and high reliability.

Table 11: FRID sensor

Operating Voltage	10-26V
power	12W
Current consumption	<0.2A
working frequency	134.2khz, 125KHZ
Recognition speed	2m/s
Card reading distance	0-180mm
Supported label types	FDX-B.EMID
Communication Interface	RS232 RS485
Working humidity	10%. 90%RH
Operating temperature	-25°C~ +70
Protection level	IP54
circuit protection	With built-in reverse polarity protection
shell material	ABS engineering plastics
By line	Binding post
installation method	M4 screws, four mounting holes

The pin functions of this module are shown in the table:

Fig. 20: FRID module pin function diagram

Since the FRID sensor outputs an RS232 signal, and C8051 does not have a dedicated RS232 interface, MAX232 needs to be used to convert the signal into a UART and then be accepted by the corresponding interface of the P1 port.

Fig. 21: Circuit of FRID sensor

Ultrasonic obstacle avoidance module: Two ultrasonic modules are placed at the front and rear of the vehicle body for obstacle detection. According to the usage conditions, choose to use the US-100 ultrasonic module.

Working principle:

When ultrasonic wave return is detected, a high-level signal of more than 10us is output.

The module continuously sends 8 40khz square waves and independently completes the signal detection.

When an ultrasonic wave returns, a high-level signal is output, and the duration is the time it takes for the ultrasonic wave to return from launch to return. It can be calculated based on the distance as the electrical signal output time multiplied by the speed of sound in the medium divided by two.

Fig. 22: Ultra-sonic sensor interface circuit

The performance parameters of the ultrasonic obstacle avoidance module are as shown in the table

Table 12: Ultrasonic module parameter table

Product name	US-100 Ultrasonic Module
Use voltage	DC2.4V-5.5V
Quiescent Current	2mA
Operating temperature	-20~+70°C
output method	Level or UART (jumper cap selection)
Sensing angle	less than 15 degrees
Detection distance	2cm-450cm
Detection accuracy	0.3cm±1%
Board size	45mm*20mm*1.6mm (there are two on the board with a radius of 1mm)
Serial configuration in UART mode	Baud rate 9600, 1 start bit, 1 stop bit, 8 data bits, no parity, no flow control

Table 13: Ultrasonic module pin function table

Pin number	Function
1	Connect to DC 2.4V~5.5V

2	When in UART mode, connect to the TX terminal; when in level trigger mode, connect to the Ttig terminal.
3	When in UART mode, connect to the RX terminal; when in level trigger mode, connect to the Echo terminal.
4	Connect to external power ground
5	Connect to external power ground

Security Edge Switch: The mechanical anti-collision mechanism was selected in the preceding article. Next, the circuit design for its built-in edge switch is completed. The edge switch's parameters are:

Table 14: Safety switch parameters

Material	Rubber
size	8*15mm
highest driving force	5N
driving distance	1mm
switching circuit	>100000
Maximum switching voltage	24V AD AC
Maximum switching current	10mA
Maximum contact resistance	≤50Ω
Maximum conversion resistance	150Ω
temperature range	-40°C to 80°C
Minimum bending radius vertical axis	750mm
horizontal axis	75mm
Dielectric strength	1500DC, 1000AC

According to the voltage requirements, a 5V DC power supply is used to power the edge switch, so that it can be directly output to the IO port of the microcontroller without the need for voltage rise and fall. The interface circuit is shown in the figure:

Fig. 23: Safety edge switch interface

Power supply voltage detection circuit: For the movement of AGV, the power sources used are rechargeable batteries. However, no matter how large the battery capacity is, there will always be a time when it is used up, and then the AGV cannot continue to work. Therefore, we need AGV to have automatic charging function to improve automation and

work efficiency. To start the automatic charging function, you must first detect whether it is under-voltage. Here we choose to use the 12-bit ADC that comes with the microcontroller for voltage detection. The input voltage range of the analog input interface of the microcontroller is AV~AGND, which is +3.3V~0V in this circuit. The battery we selected is 12V, so the battery voltage cannot be measured directly. So here we use the voltage dividing method to achieve the detection effect through the voltage division of the resistors.

For this battery, the termination voltage of this 12V series battery is 10.5V. In order to prevent under-voltage, it must be charged before reaching this voltage, so it can be set to start the automatic charging function at 10.8V voltage. As can be seen from the figure below, we use 3K and 1K resistors to divide the voltage.

$$V_o = \frac{V_i R_2}{R_1 + R_2} = 0.25V_i \tag{4.2}$$

Then the measurement range should be 3~2.7V, and the full-scale range should be 3.3V~0V, which meets the requirements. The ADC of the microcontroller is 12-bit, and its accuracy can fully meet the task requirements. Using this input voltage signal, we can convert it into a digital quantity to determine whether the voltage is sufficient and display the power supply.

Fig. 24: Voltage interface circuit

Sound and light alarm: Choose SLAS-1101J series sound and light alarm, the parameters are as follows:

Table 15: Parameter list of audible and visual alarm

Operating Voltage	DC12V
Product power	2-3W
Alarm sound	90db
Number of lamp beads	20 SMD lamp beads
Product color	Red/yellow/blue/green
Installation method	L-shaped bracket or magnetic adsorption

At the same time, this product also has a silent version that can be used as a working status indicator. In addition, in order to avoid high-voltage damage and damage, we can use optocoupler phototransistors to isolate the input and output circuits, which are used here to isolate the 12V voltage and the IO port of the microcontroller.

Fig. 25: Interface circuit of sound and light alarm

Battery selection: The power supply is AGV to facilitate mobility, the energy source is transmitted on to According to a recent AGV study, and the majority of these goods now use lead-acid batteries. Compared to other batteries, they feature more developed technology, lower pricing, and apparent performance benefits at high power and voltage. It has been widely employed in the AGV sector because to its stability, high safety factor, ease of maintenance, simplicity and applicability, plenty of material reserves, low standing power consumption, good reuse technology, and a variety of other benefits. Currently, relatively unique new lead-acid batteries for AGV have been created, increasing the usability of lead-acid batteries in the AGV market. However, lead-acid batteries also have long-standing shortcomings such as low energy storage density, short service life, heavy weight, and poor extreme performance.

AX12-45 lead-acid battery is used as the power supply, and the parameters are as follows:

Table 16: Battery parameter table

Cell voltage	Rated Capacity	internal resistance	short circuit current	Maximum charging current	Maximum discharge current	Charging temperature	Proper temperature	Charging voltage	Size	Weight
12V	45Ah	7mΩ	1250A	9A	450A	25°C	-10~40°C	13.62V, 14.2V	198×166×170mm	14.6kg

Battery capacity: Since there are many step-up and step-down modules in the circuit, it is not suitable to use the current method to check and calculate the battery capacity and usage time. Now, the relative results are obtained by calculating the power.

$$W = UIT = 1,944,000J$$

Because microcontrollers, sensors, communication modules and other parts consume less energy, circuit power consumption is now mainly calculated for modules such as voltage conversion components, drivers and sensors with high energy consumption.

Voltage conversion module: AMS1117*2, LM2577T*2;

Driver: L293E driver chip, DC speed regulator.

$$P_s = P_H + P_1 + P_2 = 93.1W \tag{4.3}$$

P_H: Power loss of the voltage regulating module

Drive power: P₁

P₂: High power sensor.

Then the battery power time is:

$$T = \frac{W}{P_S} = 20880.8s = 5.8h \tag{4.4}$$

So, from here we can say that AGV can run 5.8 hours without any difficulties

Software Part Design

The functions required by AGV are mainly magnetic navigation, FRID position information recognition, lifting and transplanting, and automatic charging functions. The following is the overall flow chart of AGV function implementation:

Fig. 26: AGV overall flowchart

Magnetic navigation design: In order to realize the design of magnetic guidance for AGV, it is necessary to establish a model of the speed of the driving wheel and the motion state of the AGV. Since this article designs a six-wheel differential drive AGV, the driven wheels theoretically have no impact on the motion state of the vehicle body. Assuming the ground is level and excluding other influencing factors, the kinematic model of the six-wheel AGV is as follows:

Fig. 27: Kinematics diagram

The XOY coordinate system in the figure is a natural coordinate system, L is the distance between the two driving wheels, and A is the speed of the driving wheel in the vehicle body coordinate system. O is the center of the car body, and V is the speed of point O. R is the turning radius. W is the angular velocity around point O. $V_l V_r$,

$$V = \frac{V_l + V_r}{2} \tag{5.1}$$

$$R = \frac{L}{2} \left[\frac{V_l + V_r}{V_l - V_r} \right] \tag{5.2}$$

$$w = \frac{V_l - V_r}{L} \tag{5.3}$$

The heading angle of the AGV is:

$$\theta_t = \theta_0 + \int_0^t w dt \quad (5.4)$$

The components of V in the x and y directions are:

$$V_x = V \cos \theta \quad (5.5)$$

$$V_y = V \sin \theta \quad (5.6)$$

The coordinates of O are:

$$x_l = x_0 + \int_0^t V_x dt \quad (5.7)$$

$$y_l = y_0 + \int_0^t V_y dt \quad (5.8)$$

When the sampling period is, the displacement increment is: Δt

$$\Delta x = vT \cos \theta \quad (5.9)$$

$$\Delta y = vT \sin \theta \quad (5.10)$$

Let the state of AGV at time t be, then $A_l = [x_l \ y_l \ \theta_l]$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_l \\ y_l \\ \theta_l \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_{t-1} & 0 \\ \sin \theta_{t-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} v_{t-1} \Delta t \\ w_{t-1} \Delta t \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.11)$$

With the dynamic model, after obtaining the initial position information of the AGV, the AGV can complete the tracking of the path trajectory by controlling the rotation speed of the two driving wheels. This provides a theoretical basis for the magnetic navigation design of AGV.

AGV path control: The AGV calculates the deviation by weighting the average of the data tags corresponding to each detection site when a magnetic field signal is observed. This approach measures the degree of variation and minimizes error.

Detecting straight lines and curves: Each detection point is assigned a different number designation based on its position. When travelling on the straight line and curved magnetic guide rail.

Detecting bifurcation intersections: If data processing is conducted at a bifurcated intersection using the straight lines and curves approach without site identification or command control, the AGV's route cannot be controlled, and derailment may occur.

This article selects bifurcated intersection pathways by modifying the data tags of the detection spots following RFID positioning:

RFID positioning: Before the AGV reaches the forked intersection, that is, the electronic tag is placed at the position before the RFID detects the magnetic signal at the forked intersection. When the FRID sensor detects this point, it uploads the data to the host computer, and the host computer will follow the planned path. Give the corresponding turn command and download the data to the microcontroller. After receiving the information, the controller selects the corresponding data tag group. Or use the corresponding commands built into the microcontroller's corresponding electronic tags to determine how to select the data tag group.

Change the deviation value of the detection point: When the AGV has to proceed straight, the impact of other magnetic navigation detection points on the deviation must be reduced, and the eight detection points should be reallocated. Similarly, when the AGV must turn in a certain direction, the deviation of the detection point pair on the opposite side must be reduced.

AGV deviation correction design

Confirmation of corrective method: If the AGV's driving speed is set to v. When the AGV deviates during the tracking process, the microcontroller obtains the deviation after processing the information from the magnetic navigation sensor. It is necessary to control the speed of the two driving wheels according to the deviation to make the AGV return to normal. The AGV returns to normal. There are mainly three types:

The speed of one round remains unchanged, and the speed of the other round increases by Δv ;

The speed of one round remains unchanged, and the speed of the other round decreases by Δv ;

The speed increases by Δv in one round and decreases to Δv in the other round.

These three back-alignment procedures can all change the status and position of the AGVs. The first two approaches adjust the AGV's speed. The first strategy increases $\Delta v/2$, but the second method decreases it. The third option keeps the AGV's speed constant. This strategy is more suited to curves in various conditions, and differential AGVs typically revert to normal using the third way. The AGV created in this article employs the third return approach to adjust its speed. PID may be utilized to regulate AGVs, calculate Δv , and improve tracking stability after identifying how they return to alignment.

PID control:

Fig. 28: PID control loop diagram

$y(t)$ It is the output physical quantity of the controlled object, which is the set target value. It is the difference between the target value and the output value, that is, it is the input quantity of the controlled object. The relationship with is: $r(t) - y(t) = e(t)$

$$u(t) = K_p[e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(t)dt + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}] \tag{5.12}$$

When performing PID control on AGV, since continuous sampling cannot be performed, it must be discretized, as follows:

$$u(k) = K_p e(k) + K_i \sum_{j=0}^k e(j) + K_d (e(k) - e(k - 1)) \tag{5.13}$$

In the formula:

$$K_i = \frac{K_p T}{T_i} \tag{5.14}$$

$$K_d = \frac{K_p T_d}{T_i} \tag{5.15}$$

The disadvantage of this method is that cumulative errors will occur when the deviations are accumulated and summed, which will also affect the data processing speed of the microcontroller. Therefore, we use incremental PID for control.

$$\Delta u(k) = u(k) - u(k - 1) \tag{5.16}$$

The expression then becomes:

$$\Delta u(k) = K_p [e(k) - e(k - 1)] + K_i e(k) + K_d [e(k) - 2e(k - 1) + e(k - 2)] \tag{5.17}$$

It can be seen that this method allows the microcontroller to process the deviation values of three sampling periods, which improves the processing efficiency.

Then, reasonable values are set according to the actual situation to complete PID control. K_p, K_i, K_d

In this paper, discrete PD control is used based on a real AGV application to minimize integral saturation and deviation buildup while also improving computation efficiency.

The deviation amount is the change amount of the PWM duty cycle that the microcontroller outputs through PD control.

$$\Delta p_{wm} = u(n) = K_p e(n) + K_d [e(n) - e(k - 1)] \tag{5.18}$$

The above describes the connection between the motor driver chip's inputs. Because the new driver chip has two H-bridge drive circuits, a DC motor must be controlled by two PWM signals, allowing the motor's two PWM inputs to

rise or decrease in relation to one another. The motor driver outputs the motor speed based on the duty cycle of the PWM signal to cause the drive wheel to revolve.

Communication design: AGV's WIFI connectivity, ultrasonic module, and RFID sensor communication all employ UART or UART-to-UART communication with full-duplex transmission.

All of these communications employ 8-bit serial transmission. When no data is transferred across the communication channel, a high level is sent. When sending and receiving information, utilize a low level as the start bit to mark the beginning of a frame of data transfer. In addition to the data bits used to transfer information, there are often parity and stop bits. The parity bit is used to check the integrity of data transmission. The stop bit is one to two high values that indicate the end of a frame of data transmission. All of the communication module settings in this article employ a one-bit parity check and a one-bit stop bit.

Economic analyses

After evaluating and learning from other AGV products on the market, this article develops a comprehensive strategy based on the task's uniqueness and similarities. It guarantees that the AGV design process is not isolated from the application market and real-world operating circumstances. The following table shows the pricing of the key electrical and mechanical components with relatively high costs in this article:

Table 17: Price list

Name	Amount	Single price/USD
ALB295A-P53 driving wheel	2	70
TYD210 support wheel	4	34.5
Xinyongtai 2480 reduction motor	2	9.5
LAP25 electric push rod	1	550
AX-12-45 battery	2	110
C8051F005	1	13.5
AGV anti-collision strip	4	34.5
W-0001 WIFI module	1	5.5
JY-L8900 FRID card reader	2	44
US100 ultrasonic obstacle avoidance module	1	3.5
Magnetic navigation sensor	1	33.5
DC motor speed regulator	1	7.9
DC speed control chip	2	0.6
7203C2ZR bearing	2	5.5
LML11 linear bearing	4	2.8

The total components in the table are 925.3USD. The main expenses are concentrated on the jacking structure and support wheels. This is an expense that cannot be reduced due to the large load of the AGV. After comprehensively considering other AGV materials and production costs, the estimated cost is about 1000USD. Compared with AGVs working in the same scene on the market, it has a great advantage in price, so it has a good market value. The performance of each component chosen for this AGV well surpasses the anticipated theoretical value, therefore mechanical and electrical performance are completely assured. The technologies and theories utilized concurrently have

been developed over a long period of time, and their applications have been well refined, assuring the safety and dependability of navigation and payloads.

Summary

This topic focuses on motor selection, major mechanical structure design, and AGV verification. Completed the design of the electrical component and the overall framework for software operation. Throughout the design process, I saw how important it was to combine knowledge and practice. Many concepts developed in the early stages were discovered to be impracticable following real component selection and strength testing. Later, depending on existing components and some research status, the plan's rationale was considerably enhanced. My software skills have substantially increased as a result of working on the AGV three-dimensional model drawing. The design of the hardware part and the drawing of circuit diagrams have exercised my data collection and electrical design abilities. In the process of completing this graduation project, I sorted out the knowledge I learned in college and deepened my understanding of this knowledge. However, this graduation project still has several flaws and places for development. It is really regrettable that we were unable to complete a final product and conduct thorough testing. The AGV's shock-absorbing system and human-machine interface's architecture and functions are also deserving of further investigation. The AGV's scheduling on the host computer is a significant challenge. Unfortunately, these components were not included in this design. I believe that this design approach will provide valuable experiences and lessons for future study and practice.

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